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Summarization of Legal Documents Using Machine Learning Models

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Abstract

Summarizing legal case judgments presents a significant challenge within the realm of Legal Natural Language Processing (NLP). There is a notable gap in understanding the effectiveness of different summarization models, such as extractive and abstractive techniques, particularly in the context of legal documents. With approximately 40 million pending cases in the Indian judicial system, this study tackles the arduous task of manually summarizing legal texts. It introduces both supervised and unsupervised models for extractive and abstractive summarization, demonstrating their efficacy through evaluations based on ROUGE metrics and BERT scores. Models such as BART, T5, PEGASUS, Legal-PEGASUS, and Legal-BERT are employed for abstractive summarization, while TextRank, LexRank, LSA, Summarizer BERT, and KL-Summ are utilized for extractive summarization. Additionally, Longformer and Bert-Legal Pegasus are considered for summarization tasks. The study leverages a hybrid abstractive-extractive techniques to generate summaries. To the best of our knowledge, this research is the first to perform an in-depth study on hybrid methods i.e. extractive-abstractive methods, specifically for legal text summarization.

Keyword—Legal, Summarization, NLP, Large Language Models, Hybrid Summarization.

1 Introduction

Legal professionals are tasked with analyzing extensive court cases to identify relevant precedents, a process that is both time-consuming and labor-intensive. In India alone, over 4.70 crore

cases are pending, underscoring the urgent need for efficient legal text processing systems [31]. Legal documents are typically lengthy, complex, and laden with domain-specific terminologies, making manual summarization impractical and costly. Automating this process is not only crucial for enhancing workflow efficiency for legal practitioners but also for improving public accessibility to judicial information [11][5][42][21]. Despite advancements in natural language processing *NLP*, legal documentation summarization, remains challenging due to the intricate narrative structures context-dependency and the need for precise legal interpretations [19]. Traditional extractive summarization methods, which select salient sentences from the original text, often yield fragmented summaries that lack contextual flow and coherence. Conversely, abstractive approaches aim to generate concise narratives but frequently suffer from semantic inconsistencies and legal inaccuracies due to rephrasing [34][26]. Additionally, most existing models are trained on general purpose corpora leading to limitations in understanding legal terminologies and syntactic structures in legal domain [29]. Recent advancements in natural language processing (NLP) have paved the way for more sophisticated approaches, particularly with the emergence of large language models *LLMs* tailored for legal application. These models leverage extensive pretraining on domain-specific corpora, demonstrating superior performance in generating contextual accurate and coherent summaries. Notable examples include SaulLM-7B for English legal text, LawGPT for Chinese legal applications, and Paramanu-AYN for Indian legal documents [6][43][27]. However, these models are predominantly trained on legal corpora specific to their jurisdiction, posing significant limitations when applied to Indian legal documents due to differences in syntactic structures, historical context, and culturally embedded terminologies. In the Indian judicial context, legal narratives are characterized by complex sentence structures, archaic language, and culturally nuanced legal concepts, which are not adequately captured by existing LLMs. This necessitates the development of domain specific models capable of handling the unique challenges posed by Indian legal texts moreover while recent LLM based model have shown promise in zero shot and few shot learning settings, they often suffer from hallucinations and inconsistencies, necessitating human oversight for ensuring legal validity and accuracy [7][22]. To address these challenges, this study proposes a novel hybrid approach that integrates extractive preprocessing using TextRank with an abstractive BART model fine-tuned on Indian legal documents. This approach is specifically designed to balance contextual accuracy, coherence, and computational efficiency while preserving legal integrity. By leveraging extractive preprocessing, the model effectively reduces input length, allowing the abstractive model to focus on generating more coherent and semantically accurate summaries. This hybrid methodology not only enhances the quality of legal tech summarization but also contributes to broader NLP applications in the legal domain. The key contributions of this study are as follows:

- Propose method: A hybrid summarization framework integrating text rank for extractive preprocessing with a fine-tuned BART model for abstractive summarization this approach ensures efficiency handling of lengthy Indian legal documents while maintaining coher-

ence and legal accuracy.

- **Extensive evaluation:** The proposed model is rigorously evaluated using multiple metrics, including ROUGE and BERTscore, across a comprehensive data set of Indian legal text. This detail evaluation demonstrates the effectiveness of the hybrid model in balancing lexical position and semantic depth.

By addressing the limitations of existing models and introducing a domain specific hybrid approach tailored for Indian legal documents, this study significantly advances the field of Legal NLP, setting a new benchmark for hybrid summarization techniques.

2 Related Works

Summarization techniques can broadly be categorized into extractive and abstractive methods, each with its unique strengths. The following discusses the existing approaches and their applications in legal text summarization.

2.1 Extractive Methods

Extractive summarization involves identifying and directly selecting the most important sentences or phrases from the original text to create a summary while preserving the exact wording. Several domain-specific techniques have been developed specifically for court document summarization. LetSum [4] and KMM [32] are two unsupervised methods that rank sentences according to term distribution models, namely TF-IDF and the k-mixture model, respectively. CaseSummerizer [28] scores sentences using a combination of TF-IDF weights and legal domain-specific characteristics. MMR [41] creates template-based summaries by combining a two-stage classifier with a Maximum Margin Relevance module. The Graphical Method [25] was found to outperform other automated summarization methods, such as LetSum, CaseSummerizer, and the Conditional Random Fields (CRF)-based Graphical Method, in summarizing legal case materials. Additionally, a novel text summarization approach for legal documents in the Indian judicial system was presented using a normalizing approach, which proved effective for extractive summarization but less useful for abstractive summarization [12]. Despite their effectiveness, extractive methods often produce fragmented narratives, lacking fluency and contextual coherence. This limitation arises from their reliance on sentence selection without content rephrasing, making them less suitable for complex legal narratives, yet remains the predominant approach in legal text processing due to the complexity of legal language, supporting the development of systems that can automatically generate summaries for large and intricate legal datasets [14]

2.2 Abstractive Methods

Abstractive summarization generates concise narratives by rephrasing and restructuring content, allowing for more coherent and contextually integrated summaries. Notable models include Pegasus, which utilizes gap-sentence generation for contextual abstraction [39], and the Pointer-Generator model that incorporates copying mechanisms to reduce information loss [33]. BERTSumAbs and BART leverage transformer architectures for semantic abstraction, enabling context-aware sentence generation [21][20]. However, these models are constrained by input length limits, making them less effective for lengthy legal documents. To overcome this, Longformer extends input capacity using sparse attention mechanisms, effectively handling long-form legal texts [3]. Additionally, LegalSumm and T5 have been adapted for legal document summarization, with T5 demonstrating superior performance in structured legal narratives [10][30].

2.3 Recent LLM-based Legal Summarization models

Recent advancements in LLM-based summarization have significantly enhanced legal text processing by leveraging domain-specific pretraining. Notable models include SaulLM-7B, LawGPT, and Paramanu-AYN, each demonstrating state-of-the-art performance in English, Chinese, and Indian legal contexts, respectively [6][43][27]. However, these models are often limited by jurisdiction-specific training corpora, impacting their effectiveness when applied to Indian legal texts, which possess unique syntactic structures and cultural nuances. To improve cross-jurisdictional performance, CLSum uses LLM-based data augmentation for common law judgments, while LexAbSumm introduces aspect-based summarization tailored to legal professionals' needs [22][38]. However, the lack of domain-specific adaptation for Indian legal texts highlights the need for more specialized models. Hybrid approaches have also shown promise. A two-step extractive-abstractive technique using BART condenses lengthy documents by summarizing key terms [2]. A divide-and-conquer strategy improves contextual flow by summarizing long texts sentence by sentence [13]. Comparative analyses show BART outperforms other transformers like T5 and RoBERTa in generating coherent legal narratives, while a BERT-GPT-2 hybrid model enhances semantic coherence [36][1]. Evaluation metrics such as ROUGE (Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation) and BERTScore are widely used to assess summarization quality, with BERTScore showing superior performance for semantic similarity in complex legal texts [40]. Despite these advancements, most models are jurisdiction-specific, limiting their adaptability to Indian legal documents. This underscores the need for developing domain-specific LLMs tailored to Indian legal texts to ensure accurate and contextually relevant summarization.

3 Baseline Models

In order to tackle the aforementioned problems, we conducted experiments on hybrid models that may accurately summarize legal documents and procedures while also effectively capturing their context. Below is an explanation of the baseline model BART.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the Pretrained BART model.

3.0.1 BART

We used a publicly available implementation of the transformer-based sequence-to-sequence architecture known as BART [20] as a base model for summarizing long legal documents. This model was pretrained on the Colossal Clean Crawled Corpus (C4) without being fine-tuned on domain-specific tasks. The pre-trained BART model, which is intended for general-purpose summarization, was utilized directly to generate summaries for each input chunk. To ensure compatibility with the model’s architecture, each document was broken down into subword token sequences of up to 1,024 tokens. A sliding window approach, which divides the text into overlapping portions of manageable size, was used to handle documents that exceeded this token limit. This method made sure that during preprocessing, no important information was lost. The model generated tokenized outputs that represented the abstractive summaries after receiving the tokenized input. The ‘decode’ method of the BART tokenizer was then used to decode the generated summary back into human-readable language, making sure that any special tokens or padding had been eliminated. We employed standard metrics, such as BERTScore, which computes the semantic similarity scores using the pretrained BERT model, to assess the model’s capacity to capture important information, and ROUGE, which measures n-gram (max n set to 2) overlaps between the generated summaries and reference summaries, to appraise the quality of the summaries. Using its generalized knowledge from training on a large corpus, the pre-trained BART model showed sufficient skills in producing lucid and succinct summaries even in the absence of fine-tuning. This methodology provides a baseline approach for extracting important information from complicated documents and demonstrates the efficacy of using state-of-the-art transformer models for legal text summarization, even without domain-specific adaptation.

3.0.2 FineTuned-BART

We utilized the same pre-trained BART model to fine-tune it for generating abstractive summaries of judicial documents. The training process began with dataset preparation, where pairs of judicial documents and their corresponding summaries were organized into separate directories. A custom data set class was developed using PyTorch’s ‘Data Set ‘ module to facilitate the loading and processing of these document-summary pairs. Each judicial document (input) and its summary (target) were tokenized using the BART tokenizer, ensuring sequences adhered to a maximum length of 1,024 tokens for inputs and 512 tokens for outputs. This tokenization step involved truncating or padding the sequences to standardize them for the transformer model. The

Figure 2: Block Diagram of the Finetuned BART model.

fine-tuning process was designed to optimize the model’s performance for the domain-specific task of summarizing lengthy legal texts. We employed the Hugging Face Trainer API to streamline this process, providing it with the initialized BART model, a tokenizer for compatibility, and the prepared training and validation datasets. The training configuration included key hyperparameters, which are detailed in Table 1. The model was trained for 10 epochs, with evaluation conducted at the end of each epoch to monitor its performance on the validation set. To enhance computational efficiency, mixed-precision training (FP16) was enabled, allowing the model to leverage GPU acceleration for faster computations. Throughout the fine-tuning process, model checkpoints were saved at the end of each epoch, with a limit on the total number of saved versions to optimize storage usage. The evaluation phase involved monitoring validation loss and calculating ROUGE scores to assess the quality of the generated summaries. These scores measured the overlap between the model-generated summaries and the reference summaries, providing insights into the model’s ability to retain critical information and produce coherent, domain-specific outputs. This fine-tuning approach effectively adapted the pre-trained BART model for legal text summarization, enabling it to generate concise, abstractive summaries that align with the unique requirements of judicial documents.

Figure 3: Block Diagram of the TextRank and Finetuned BART hybrid model.

4 Proposed Methodology

4.1 Hybrid Summarization Framework using TextRank-Finetuned BART

This methodology integrates extractive summarization using the TextRank algorithm with abstractive summarization leveraging a fine-tuned BART model. The proposed framework is designed to process lengthy legal documents efficiently by first distilling key content through extractive techniques before generating refined summaries via neural sequence-to-sequence learning. The summarization pipeline consists of four primary stages: (1) Extractive summarization using TextRank, (2) Fine-tuning the BART model, (3) Generating abstractive summaries, and (4) Evaluating the generated summaries using robust evaluation metrics. The process begins with dataset preparation, where legal judgments are matched with their corresponding reference summaries based on filenames to ensure consistency. Preprocessing steps include verifying encoding compatibility and ensuring accessibility of input files for summarization tasks.

4.2 Extractive and Abstractive Summarization

The extractive summarization step employs the TextRank algorithm from the Sumy library. Each judgment is first tokenized into sentences using Sumy’s `PlaintextParser` and `Tokenizer`. A graph-based ranking model is then applied, where sentence similarity is computed, and nodes (sentences) are ranked based on their centrality. The highest-ranked sentences, comprising 30% of the document, are selected as the extractive summary. These summaries, along with the original judgments and reference summaries, are stored in JSON format to maintain structural fidelity for subsequent processing. For the abstractive summarization stage, the extractive sum-

maries serve as input for a fine-tuned BART model. A custom PyTorch Dataset class tokenizes the extractive summaries (input) and reference summaries (target) using the BART tokenizer, applying padding and truncation to ensure uniform tensor dimensions. The tokenization process limits inputs to 1,024 tokens and targets to 512 tokens. The `bart-large-cnn` model is initialized with its tokenizer and configured for sequence-to-sequence abstractive summarization. Fine-tuning follows the hyperparameter settings outlined in Table 1. To optimize performance, training employs early stopping after three epochs without improvement in validation loss. Gradient clipping is implemented to mitigate exploding gradients, and a cosine learning rate scheduler with warmup steps ensures smooth convergence. The best model, determined based on validation loss, is stored for inference. For inference, the extractive summaries are fed into the fine-tuned BART model’s `generate` function. Beam search is employed to enhance fluency, with a maximum output length of 512 tokens and early stopping enabled to prevent redundant outputs. Generated summaries are decoded and stored as JSON files, containing both extractive and reference summaries. Evaluation is performed using ROUGE metrics (ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, ROUGE-L) and BERTScore to quantitatively assess summary quality.

4.3 Summary Length Control and Observations

A crucial aspect of this methodology is explicit control over summary length, ensuring a balance between extractive and abstractive summarization techniques. Unlike unconstrained approaches, which rely entirely on model inference, we incorporate length constraints to enhance efficiency and readability. The extractive summarization stage employs a fixed ratio parameter of 0.3, selecting 30% of the document’s sentences. This ensures adequate content retention while reducing redundancy, thereby improving the effectiveness of the subsequent abstractive summarization phase. For the abstractive summarization phase, the maximum output length is explicitly defined through the `max_length` parameter in the `generate()` function:

```
generated_ids = model.generate(  
    extractive_summary,  
    max_length=512,  
    num_beams=5,  
    early_stopping=True )
```

This constraint prevents excessively verbose outputs while allowing the model flexibility in determining an optimal stopping point. The combination of beam search and length restriction ensures both fluency and conciseness.

Table 1: Hyper-parameters used in fine-tuning BART.

Hyperparameter	Value
Learning rate	1e-5
Batch size	8
Epochs	10
Weight decay	0.01
FP16	True
LR scheduler type	cosine
Patience	3

5 Experimental Details

5.1 Dataset

The dataset IN-Abs (<http://www.liiofindia.org/in/cases/cen/INSC/>) used in this study consists of 7130 legal judgments specifically curated for abstractive summarization of Indian legal documents. Of these, 7030 documents were used for fine-tuning the model, with 90% allocated for training and 10% for validation. The remaining 100 documents were used as the test set. The average length of the judgments is 4,378 tokens, while the corresponding summaries average 1,051 tokens, reflecting the complexity and verbosity typical of Indian legal texts. To maintain consistency and reliability, the dataset was preprocessed by:

- Removing special characters, redundant whitespace, and HTML tags.
- Normalizing text to ensure uniform representation of entities such as dates, monetary values, and legal citations.

This dataset design ensures comprehensive coverage of legal terminology and narrative structures prevalent in Indian judiciary documents, facilitating effective model training and evaluation.

5.2 Model Hyperparameters

Table 1 details the hyperparameters used for fine-tuning the BART model in the hybrid summarization framework. The BART model (bart-large-cnn) was initialized using the Hugging Face Transformers library, and fine-tuning was conducted using the Hugging Face Trainer API. Mixed-precision training (FP16) was enabled to optimize computational efficiency on NVIDIA GPUs. Pre-trained models used in this study:

- BART (bart-large-cnn): <https://huggingface.co/facebook/bart-large-cnn>
- Legal BERT: <https://huggingface.co/nlpaueb/legal-bert-base-uncased>

Table 2: Document-wide ROUGE and BERTScores on IN-Abs Dataset, averaged over 100 test documents. Baseline model results are sourced from [24] with permission from the author.

Model	ROUGE-1	ROUGE-2	ROUGE-L	BERTScore
<i>Abstractive Methods</i>				
T5	0.12	0.02	0.10	0.57
Pegasus	0.30	0.06	0.17	0.75
Roberta	0.34	0.04	0.19	0.64
BART	0.32	0.09	0.18	0.69
Legal Pegasus	0.43	0.12	0.27	0.77
Legal BERT	0.19	0.05	0.27	0.62
<i>Extractive Methods</i>				
LSA	0.30	0.07	0.14	0.71
Lex Rank	0.42	0.11	0.16	0.82
Text Rank	0.44	0.12	0.18	0.85
KL Summ	0.20	0.06	0.19	0.63
BERT	0.28	0.07	0.14	0.59
<i>Hybrid Methods</i>				
BERT-BART	0.34	0.11	0.21	0.81
BERT-Pegasus	0.25	0.07	0.14	0.73
Proposed Methods				
Finetuned BART	0.47	0.23	0.25	0.15
TextRank_Pretrained BART	0.28	0.15	0.18	0.04
TextRank_Finetuned BART	0.49	0.25	0.26	0.16

5.3 Evaluation metrics

The effectiveness of the proposed hybrid summarization model was evaluated using the following metrics:

- **ROUGE:** Measures the overlap of n-grams between generated summaries and reference summaries. Metrics used: ROUGE-1 (unigram), ROUGE-2 (bigram), and ROUGE-L (longest common subsequence). Library used: ROUGE Score from the rouge-score Python package.
- **BERTScore:** Evaluates semantic similarity by comparing embeddings of generated summaries and reference summaries. It leverages contextual embeddings from pre-trained BERT models, providing a more nuanced assessment of semantic accuracy. Library used: BERTScore available on GitHub.

These metrics collectively provide a comprehensive evaluation by balancing lexical overlap and semantic alignment, ensuring the generated summaries are both accurate and contextually coherent.

5.4 Libraries and Tools Used

The implementation was carried out using the following libraries:

- Hugging Face Transformers: <https://huggingface.co/transformers>
- PyTorch: <https://pytorch.org>
- NLTK: <https://www.nltk.org>
- ROUGE Score: <https://pypi.org/project/rouge-score>
- BERTScore: https://pypi.org/project/bert_score
- existing Abstractive and extractive methods: <https://github.com/Law-AI/summarization>

6 Results and Analysis

This section presents an in-depth analysis of the summarization models evaluated in our study. The findings are categorized into different subsections to facilitate clarity and comparison.

6.1 Extractive Summarization Evaluation

Extractive summarization techniques aim to retain the most significant portions of a legal document by selecting salient sentences while preserving their original wording. Among the evaluated methods, **TextRank** demonstrated the highest effectiveness, achieving ROUGE-1 (0.44), ROUGE-2 (0.12), and ROUGE-L (0.18). **LexRank** also performed well, attaining a strong BERTScore (0.82), indicating its ability to capture essential legal content. Despite their reliability in preserving factual accuracy, extractive methods often produce summaries that are fragmented and lack a coherent narrative structure. These models are inherently limited by their inability to paraphrase content, which results in summaries that may be lexically precise but semantically disjointed. However, their efficiency in selecting critical legal statements makes them useful for cases where factual correctness is paramount.

6.2 Abstractive Summarization Evaluation

Abstractive summarization models generate concise summaries by reinterpreting and restructuring textual content rather than merely extracting sentences. Among the evaluated abstractive methods, **Legal Pegasus** achieved the best performance, with ROUGE-1 (0.43), ROUGE-2 (0.12), and ROUGE-L (0.27), alongside a strong BERTScore (0.77). This model displayed superior semantic understanding and fluency in rephrasing complex legal texts. Other abstractive models such as **BART** and **RoBERTa** performed moderately well but struggled with the syntactic complexity and domain-specific terminology in legal documents. While abstractive models offer improved coherence and readability, they introduce the risk of semantic drift, where reworded content may misrepresent legal nuances. Ensuring legal accuracy remains a challenge in this category, highlighting the need for domain-specific training and legal oversight.

6.3 Proposed Hybrid Method Evaluation

The **Hybrid TextRank-Finetuned BART model** integrates extractive preprocessing with abstractive summarization to balance lexical accuracy with contextual depth. This approach first extracts key content via TextRank, reducing document length, before passing it to a fine-tuned BART model for abstractive summarization. The hybrid model achieved the highest ROUGE-1 (0.49) and ROUGE-2 (0.25) scores while maintaining a competitive ROUGE-L (0.26). Despite its strong performance, the hybrid approach remains biased towards extraction, as indicated by its lower BERTScore. While it effectively retains legal terminology and key legal facts, it does not always achieve the same level of abstraction as fully abstractive models like Legal Pegasus. However, it mitigates the fragmentation issues of pure extractive models while reducing the risk of hallucinations in abstractive methods, making it a viable solution for legal document summarization.

6.4 Comparative Model Performance

Table 2 highlights the diverse strengths and limitations of the evaluated models, emphasizing the trade-offs between lexical precision and semantic depth. Legal Pegasus excels in generating semantically rich abstractive summaries, while TextRank reliably captures extractive content with high lexical overlap. The Hybrid TextRank-Finetuned BART model bridges the gap with robust performance in lexical evaluation metrics like ROUGE. For abstractive summarization, Legal Pegasus achieves the highest scores in ROUGE-1 (0.43), ROUGE-2 (0.12), and ROUGE-L (0.27), demonstrating its exceptional capacity to generate summaries with a strong lexical and semantic presence. Additionally, the BERTScore (0.77) for abstractive summarization further validates its effectiveness. BART and RoBERTa perform moderately as well. Among extractive methods, TextRank emerges as the most effective model, achieving the highest ROUGE-1 (0.44), ROUGE-2 (0.12), and ROUGE-L (0.18) scores. LexRank also performs admirably, demonstrating its ability to capture crucial information for extraction with high ROUGE-1 (0.42) and a notable BERTScore (0.82). Overall, TextRank is the most reliable extractive summarization method, while KL-Summ, LSA, and BERT also perform reasonably well.

6.5 Summary Length and Model Performance

In Table 3, we observe a significant decrease in word length after the summarization task has been performed. Table 6.6 illustrates a sample of a generated summary after a document was processed through the summarization pipeline. A Hybrid TextRank-Finetuned BART model outperforms other models in ROUGE-1 (0.49) and ROUGE-2 (0.25). Although Legal Pegasus and Legal BERT achieve higher ROUGE-L scores, the hybrid model remains competitive, as shown in Table 2. However, its lower BERTScore suggests that it is primarily extractive, consisting of verbatim text segments or lexical patterns. While these summaries effectively

capture legal terms and statutes, they lack the abstraction or paraphrasing needed to convey reasoning or intent. In summary, when focusing on ROUGE scores, the Hybrid model performs best. However, for BERTScore, TextRank leads in extractive summarization, and Legal Pegasus remains the strongest abstractive method.

6.6 Observations and Findings

During our implementation, we observed that while the fixed 30% extractive ratio and 512-token abstractive cap provided a good balance between information retention and summary conciseness, a more adaptive length control strategy could further enhance summarization quality. Specifically:

- **Fixed 0.3 Ratio in Extractive Summarization:** While effective in most cases, a dynamic ratio based on document length could improve flexibility. For instance, longer documents might require a smaller extractive ratio, while shorter ones may need a slightly higher ratio to retain sufficient content.
- **Fixed max_length=512 in Abstractive Summarization:** This setting effectively prevents excessively long summaries. However, in certain cases, dynamically adjusting the length based on document complexity (e.g., scaling max_length with the extractive summary size) could yield more coherent results.

Legal Pegasus excels in abstractive summarization, offering high semantic alignment and lexical coverage, while TextRank remains the most reliable extractive model, achieving strong ROUGE and BERT scores. The Hybrid TextRank-Finetuned BART model effectively balances abstractive and extractive elements but leans towards extractive summaries. Adaptive length control could further refine summarization quality by dynamically adjusting extractive ratios and abstractive length constraints. Thus, while summary length was not entirely left to the model, we also did not impose rigid constraints that might hinder fluency and coherence. Instead, we adopted a hybrid strategy that optimally balances extractive preprocessing and abstractive generation to ensure both legal relevance and readability. Future work could focus on refining hybrid approaches to balance these trade-offs and enhance both lexical and semantic metrics, ensuring comprehensive and contextually meaningful legal document summaries.

Table 3: Comparison of word lengths between raw judgment and generated summary.

Document	Total Word Length
Raw judgment document	5272
Summary generated by TextRank-Finetuned BART model	444

Example Generated Summary

id: "2096"

title: "Appeal No. 274 of 1964."

abstractive_summary:

The buyer entered into a second contract with the seller for the purchase of 24 drums of the same material. The seller negotiated the bills of lading with the Marine Midland Trust Company, New York and obtained payment of U.S. \$6,998.75 under the letters of credit. The buyer paid the amount to the Eastern Bank Limited, Madras, and the buyer paid to the said Bank a sum of Rs.96,000. The cause of action against the ship-owners was that they made a misrepresentation that the bills were clean whereas in fact they were not so. The High Court dismissed the suit against the Ship-owners but decreed it in part against the Bank. The Bank and the ship owners preferred appeals to the High Court against the said decree insofar as it went against each of them. The judge held that the Bank was liable to refund the amount paid only under one of the Letters of credit and that even if the bills had been unclean, the Bank would still have paid the money. He also said that the oldness or newness of drums had no real impact on the contents thereof, for both, were equally suitable containers of the articles to be supplied. The plaintiffs also charge that the defendants are precluded from denying the correctness of the statement in regards to the good order and condition of the bills. The second defendants are liable for issuing the bills without disclosing the true facts of the state of the lading which are admitted to be untrue. The third defendants are also liable for not disclosing the truth about the bills and for inserting statements in the bills which are not true and which are now possible to enable the shippers to obtain moneys against which they agreed to be sold which were not agreed to. The fourth defendant is liable for the false statement that the goods were not in good condition and that they were in need of repair. The fifth defendant and the sixth defendant are liable to pay back the money that was paid to them under the terms of the contract which they had entered into with the buyer for the sale of the drums. The last defendant is also liable to repay the money which was paid by the buyer under the letter of credit under which the drums were to be purchased. The case was heard at the Supreme Court of India and the verdict was delivered on November 14, 2013. The decision was delivered by Justice Ravi Agrawal. The judgment was delivered in the absence of a jury. The jury was unable to reach a verdict.

In Table 3, we can see a significant decrease in word length after the summarization task has been performed. The example above shows a sample generated summary after a document was

fed into the summarization pipeline. The results in Table 2 highlight the diverse strengths and limitations of the evaluated models, emphasizing the trade-offs between lexical precision and semantic depth. While Legal Pegasus excels in generating semantically rich abstractive summaries, and TextRank reliably captures extractive content with high lexical overlap, the Hybrid TextRank-Finetuned BART model bridges the gap with robust performance in lexical evaluation metrics like ROUGE. This analysis underscores the importance of selecting a summarization approach tailored to the specific requirements of a task, whether prioritizing semantic alignment for interpretive contexts or lexical accuracy for precise, fact-based content. Future work could focus on further refining hybrid approaches to balance these trade-offs and enhance both lexical and semantic metrics, ensuring comprehensive and contextually meaningful legal document summaries.

7 Conclusion and Future Work

This research makes a meaningful contribution to legal text summarization by introducing a novel approach that enhances text summarization models across various legal domains. The hybrid model proposed in this study has the potential to serve as a valuable tool for both researchers and practitioners engaged in legal summarization tasks, allowing them to generate high-quality summaries of legal texts more efficiently. Looking ahead, we plan to explore ways to further refine our approach, particularly in improving performance on BERTScore. One challenge encountered involves guiding the BART model to generate summaries that align with the critical components legal experts expect, namely, Facts, Legal Provisions, and Judgments. BART, being a sophisticated transformer model, requires significant computational resources, which can be a limiting factor, especially when dealing with large datasets or constrained hardware. Additionally, the extensive training time necessary for these large-scale transformer models can slow down the process of experimenting with different model designs and tuning hyperparameters, an essential aspect of machine learning research. In future work, we aim to examine how multi-label classifiers capture contextual meaning and explore the potential application of this technique in other text summarization fields. Further research should focus on addressing the limitations identified in this study, particularly improving semantic alignment to enhance BERTScore results. Implementing strategies such as reinforcement learning with semantic-based reward functions or optimizing both lexical and semantic evaluation metrics simultaneously could lead to a more balanced and effective summarization approach. Moreover, advancing domain-specific pretraining methods, such as fine-tuning legal Pegasus or BART using legal-specific datasets, may further enhance the model's ability to generate summaries that align with the nuances of legal language. Another promising direction involves leveraging multi-label classification to better segment and summarize distinct sections of legal documents. By more effectively identifying key components such as Facts, Legal Provisions, and Judgments, this approach could improve both the interpretability and practical usefulness of the generated

summaries.

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